

VALIDATION OF ITRACONAZOLE IN BULK FORM USING UV SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC METHOD

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Abstract

New, simple and cost effective UV-spectrophotometric method was developed for the estimation of Itraconazole in bulk formulations. Itraconazole was estimated at 263 nm in 25% Methanol. Linearity range was found to be 10–50 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ (regression equation: $0.0216 + 0.1804x$; $r^2 = 0.9961$). The apparent molar absorptivity was found to be $2.79 \times 10^4 \text{ l mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in 25% Methanol. The method was tested and validated for various parameters according to ICH guidelines and USP. The quantitation limits were found to be 0.3908 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ and 0.118 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ in 25% Methanol respectively. The results demonstrated that the procedure is accurate, precise and reproducible (relative standard deviation < 2%), while being simple, cheap and less time consuming and can be suitably applied for the estimation of Itraconazole in different dosage forms and dissolution studies.

Keywords: Itraconazole, Methanol Spectrophotometry; Validation

1. INTRODUCTION

Itraconazole (figure-1) is a (ITZ)-1-(butan-2-yl)-4-{4-[4-(4-[(2R,4S)-2-(2,4-dichlorophenyl)-2-(1H-1,2,4-triazol-1-ylmethyl)-1,3-dioxolan-4-yl] methoxy} phenyl) piperazin-1-yl]phenyl}-4,5-dihydro-1H-1,2,4-triazol-5-one. It is a fungistatic with broader spectrum of activity than ketoconazole or fluconazole. Itraconazole works principally by inhibition of cytochrome P450 14 α -demethylase (P45014DM). This enzyme is in the sterol biosynthesis pathway that leads from lanosterol to ergosterol. Itraconazole shows a low bioavailability of 55% due to presystemic metabolism. Hepatic impairment will therefore increase its bioavailability. The oral bioavailability of itraconazole appears to be maximal when taken with a full meal. Itraconazole is metabolized predominately by the cytochrome P450 3A4 λ hydroxyitraconazole, the major metabolite. The duration of action of a single oral dose is longer than the half-life and may be up to 3-4 days. Steady state is reached in 14 days. [1] A Survey of literature has revealed estimation of itraconazole in Plasma by High-Performance Liq Chromatography with Fluorescence Detection[3], . Isocratic High Performance Liquid Chromatographic Method with UV detection for simultaneous determination of voriconazole and itraconazole and its hydroxyl metabolite in human serum. [4] Simultaneous determination of itraconazole and hydroxyitraconazole in human plasma by high performance liquid chromatography,[5]. A. Spectrofluorimetric Determination of Itraconazole in Dosage Forms and Spiked Human Plasma was reported [6] Recently a uv spectrophotometric for estimation of itraconazole was also reported [7] Determination of azole antifungal medicines using zero-order and derivative uv spectrophotometry, Liquid Chromatographic Method for the Determination of Plasma Itraconazole and Its Hydroxy Metabolite in Pharmacokinetic/Bioavailability Studies[8] Rapid and Sensitive High Performance Liquid Chromatographic Method for the Determination of Itraconazole and its Hydroxy-Metabolite in Human Serum[9], Spectrophotometric Method Development and Validation of Itraconazole in its bulk and Dosage Form[10]. Chromatographic techniques are costly and time consuming, hence a simple and accurate spectrophotometric method in analysis of bulk and dissolution samples is highly recommended. The objective of present work is to develop simple, accurate, precise and economic analytical method with good detection range for estimation of itraconazole in bulk dosage forms. A simple method has been developed for estimation of itraconazole, medium used is 25% methanol (λ_{\max} -263nm). The developed

method was validated as per ICH guidelines and USP requirements [11, 12], suitable statistical tests were performed on validation data [13].

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Absorption Maximum

In order to ascertain the wavelength of maximum absorbance (λ_{\max}) the solution with particular concentration of drug 10 μ g/ml in 25% methanol was scanned within the wavelength range of 200-400nm against a corresponding reagent blank. The resulting spectrum shows absorption curve with unique characteristic absorption maximum at 263nm. The absorption spectrum of Itraconazole is given in (figure-2)

2.2 Preparation of Stock Solutions

10 mg of Itraconazole was accurately weighed and dissolved in 100 ml of 25% methanol in 100ml volumetric flask to get the concentration about 100 μ g/ml stock solution.

2.3 Preparation of Calibration curve

From the above stock solution prepare serial dilutions from 1 ml to 5 ml and transfer it to 10ml volumetric flasks. Dilute it with 25% methanol to get the concentrations ranging from 10 μ g/ml to 50 μ g/ml respectively. The absorbances were measured at λ_{\max} 263 nm against 25% methanol as a blank. Results are shown in (Table-1). The calibration curve was shown in (figure-3)

3. Method validation

3.1 Specificity

Itraconazole solution (6 μ g/ml) was prepared in 25% methanol along with and without common excipients (starch, dextrose, benzalkonium chloride, magnesium stearate) separately. All the solutions were scanned from 450 to 200 nm and checked for change in the absorbance at respective wavelengths. In a separate study, drug concentration of 6 μ g ml⁻¹ was prepared independently from pure drug stock in 25% methanol and analysed ($N = 5$).

Paired *t*-test at 95% level of significance was performed to compare the means of absorbance (**Table 2**).

3.2 Accuracy

As a part of determining accuracy of the proposed method, drug concentrations were prepared from independent stock solution and analyzed ($N = 9$). Accuracy was assessed as mean percentage recovery (**Table 3**).

3.3 Precision

Repeatability was determined by using three different levels of drug concentrations (prepared from independent stock solution and analyzed ($N = 9$)) (**Table 4**). Inter-day and intra-day variation and instrument variations were taken to determine intermediate precision of the proposed methods. Different levels of drug concentrations in triplicates were prepared three different times in a day and studied for intra-day variation. Same protocol was followed for three different days to study inter-day variation ($N = 27$).

3.4 Linearity

The linearity is established for the proposed method, nine separate series of solutions of the drug ($10\text{-}50\ \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ in 25% Methanol medium) were prepared from the stock solutions and analyzed. Least square regression analysis is done for the obtained data. ANOVA test (one-way) was performed based on the absorbance values observed for each pure drug concentration during the replicate measurement of the standard solutions.

3.5 Detection limit (DL) and quantitation limit (QL)

Detection limit (DL) and quantitation limit (QL) for the proposed method is determined by using calibration standards. DL and QL were calculated as $3.3r/S$ and $10r/S$, respectively, where S is the slope of the calibration curve and r is the standard deviation of y -intercept of regression equation (**Table 5**).

3.6 Robustness

Robustness of the proposed method is determined by (a) changing strength of the medium by $\pm 2\%$ and (b) stability of the Itraconazole in the medium at room temperature for 8 hrs. Three different concentrations (LQC, MQC and HQC) were prepared in medium with different strength. Mean percentage recovery was determined (**Table 6**).

4. Results and discussions

For media optimization various aqueous media like acetate buffers (pH 3.6–5.8), phosphate buffers (pH 5.8–8.0) and 0.1N sodium hydroxide were investigated. Itraconazole showed UV absorption spectra in 25% Methanol. The final decision of using 25% methanol as the medium is based on criteria like; sensitivity of the method, cost, ease of preparation and applicability of the method to dissolution studies. The spectra of Itraconazole in the 25% Methanol are shown in Fig. 2 the lambda max of Itraconazole in 25% Methanol is found to be 263 nm. Apparent molar absorptivity of drug was found to be $2.79 \times 10^4 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in 25% Methanol (**Table 2**). The linear regression equation obtained is: absorbance at 263nm = $0.0216 + 0.1804$ with a regression coefficient of 0.9999 (**Table 2**).

4.1. Analytical validation

4.2. Specificity and selectivity

The UV-spectrum of Itraconazole was not changed in the presence of common excipients in 25% Methanol. The calculated *t*-values were found to be less than that of the critical *t*-value, indicating that statistically there was no significant difference between mean absorbance of solutions prepared from pure drug sample (**Table 2**). Therefore proposed methods are specific and selective for the drug.

4.3. Accuracy

The excellent % recovery values (nearly 100%) and their low standard deviation values (S.D. < 1.5) represent accuracy. In 25% methanol the mean percentage recoveries (% R.S.D.) for lower, intermediate and higher concentrations were found to be 100.05(0.575), 99.59 (2.059) and 99.4 (1.03). This result revealed that any small change in the drug concentration in the solution can be accurately determined by these proposed methods.

4.4 Precision

Precision determined by studying repeatability and intermediate precision. Repeatability (% R.S.D.) in 25% methanol, at all three levels of concentrations (**Table 4**). Repeatability results indicate the precision under the same operating conditions over a short interval of time and inter-assay precision. Intermediate precision expresses within-laboratory variations in different days and in different instruments. In intermediate precision study, % R.S.D. values were not more than 2.5% in all the cases (**Table 4**). R.S.D. values were within the acceptable range indicating that these methods have excellent repeatability and intermediate precision.

4.5 Linearity

In 25% methanol the linearity range was found to be 10–50 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ at 263 nm. Lower values of parameters like standard error of slope and intercept (**Table 2**) indicated high precision of the proposed methods.

4.6 DL and QL

In 25% Methanol DL and QL were found to be 0.3908 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ and 0.118 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ respectively.

4.7 Robustness

Variation of strength in the selected medium by $\pm 2\%$ did not have any significant effect on absorbance. The mean % recovery (\pm S.D.) were found to be 100.39(\pm 0.284) in the 25% methanol respectively (**Table 6**).

5. Conclusion

In summary, the proposed method was simple, rapid, accurate, precise and inexpensive and can be used for routine analysis of Itraconazole in bulk, pharmaceutical formulations and for dissolution studies.

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Figure-1

Wave length**Figure-3****Calibration curve of Itraconazole****Table-1****Calibration data of the developed method**

(Each value is result of nine separate determinations)

Sno	Concentration(mcg/ml)	Absorbance at 263nm±(SD)	%RSD
1	10	0.398±0.00578	1.48
2	20	0.599±0.01168	1.99
3	30	0.812±0.0207	2.49
4	40	1.045±0.0203	2.27
5	50	1.230±0.0127	1.03

S.D: Standard deviation, %RSD: Relative standard deviation

Table-2**Optical Characteristics and Regression Equation of Itraconazole**

$Y^* = ax+b$, where 'x' is concentration in $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and Y is absorbance

Parameters	Itraconazole
Apparent molar absorptivity ($l \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$)	2.79×10^4
Linearity range ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	10-50
Correlation coefficient	0.9961
Regression equation (Y)*	
Slope (a)	0.0216
Intercept (b)	0.1804
Slope(s.e)	0.000198
Calculated <i>F</i> -value (critical <i>F</i> -value) ^a	2.07(2.305)
Specificity and selectivity - t_{Cal} (t_{Crit}) ^b	0.366(2.353)
DL (mcg/ml)	0.03908
QL(mcg/ml)	0.1184
Robustness (mean % recovery \pm S.D.)	0.284

^a Theoretical value of $F(4,45)$ based on one-way ANOVA test at $P = 0.05$ level of significance.

^b t_{Cal} is calculated value and t_{Crit} is theoretical value (at 8 d.f.) based on paired t-test at $P = 0.05$ level of significance

Table 3**Accuracy data of the developed method**

Sno	Concentration(mcg/ml)	Mean Absorbance	S.D	%RSD	%Recovery
1	10	0.389	0.00228	0.57522	100.05
2	20	0.586	0.00352	0.593	100.32
3	30	0.832	0.01739	2.05618	99.59
4	40	1.045	0.00493	0.46203	100.13
5	50	1.2307	0.01276	1.03662	99.4

S.D-Standard Deviation, %RSD-Relative Standard Deviation

Table 4**Precision data of the developed method**

Sno	Concentration (mcg/ml)	Intra-day repeatability % R.S.D(N = 9)			Inter-day repeatability % R.S.D (N = 27)
		Day 1	Day 2	Day 3	
1	10	0.396	0.398	0.392	0.631
2	30	0.867	0.846	0.821	2.23
3	50	1.212	1.237	1.238	0.978

Table 5**Detection limit (DL) and quantitation limit (QL) data for the developed method**

Sno		Mean of calibration curve (N=9)	SD	DL	QL
1	Slope	0.0213			
2	Intercept	0.1806	0.00026	0.3908	0.11842
3	R ²	0.9961			

Table 6**Robustness data for the developed method**

Sno	Concentration(mcg/ml)	Mean Absorbance (N=9)	S.D	%Recovery	%Recovery of SD
1	10	0.395	0.002	100.17	0.284
2	30	0.846	0.018	100.39	
3	50	1.229	0.012	100.73	